

The Endless Hunger Rates in the U.S: Poverty's Crime

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The current world population is 7.8 billion people; a number so extensive that it's almost imaginable. With our world changing so fast, humanity is creating a greater population, advancing new technology, and boosting the economy and resources. It's truly remarkable, but what about the image of humanity that rarely is shown. Poverty, hunger, and chaos. The sad truth is that there are so many people who don't know when their next meal will be. People are suffering from hunger and poverty in a world full of plenty. According to Feeding America, in 2018, more than 37 million people - 11 million being children - have fought against hunger in the United States.¹ Many people believe that in a first world country like the United States, the rate of poverty wouldn't be high, yet nearly two-thirds of people face hunger and have incomes that are barely above the federal poverty line.

Our country genuinely has enough resources to ensure that our people would not go hungry, yet we see an abundance of hungriness. This is mainly caused by poverty that results from a lack of jobs or because jobs pay too little. If we truly want to build a future where hunger is essentially eliminated, we must all get involved.

There are several issues that lead to hunger in America and they have not been fully resolved. In the U.S many states are shown to have high economic rates, yet the majority of the citizens who don't live in affluent neighborhoods struggle to have meals, and are barely paid enough money to live comfortably from their jobs. Lack of investment in communities to help those who are unable to be food secure, is not as uncommon as many believe and is becoming more apparent. Food insecurity exists throughout America, and its impact on minorities and on children is wide-ranging and affects many well-documented aspects of children's and their families' lives. The U.S is sufficient enough to provide an abundance of resources, so why do so many Americans still go hungry? Studies from the Department of Agriculture have shown that in 2016, about 14% of households - 48 million people - have gone hungry during the year, and not out of their free will.² Enough is enough. If we can't use our vast knowledge, sources, voices and funds to implement change, then how can we advocate for a better world?

¹ Feeding America. (2020). Facts About Hunger and Poverty In America. Retrieved August 5, 2020, from <https://www.feedingamerica.org/hunger-in-america/facts>

² The Conversation. (2016). U.S is a Land of Plenty, so Why Do Americans Go Hungry?. Retrieved August 6, 2020, from <https://theconversation.com/u-s-is-a-land-of-plenty-so-why-do-millions-of-americans-still-go-hungry-55791>

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As Jeff Bridges once said, “*One of the greatest feelings in the world is knowing that we as individuals can make a difference. Ending hunger in America is a goal that is literally within our grasp.*” It’s not rocket science, that our country has more than enough resources to feed the hungry and the poor. What we need is strong resolve to push through and demand our people have the money and food in order to live. Implementing awareness and action into America’s larger food corporations and budget will effectively contribute to the elimination of hunger, poverty, and food insecurity.

In a first-world country like America, there is unimaginable hunger lingering in the streets and homes of many individuals. There are more than 37 million Americans that struggle against hunger who live in households. Now just imagine all the people who don’t have stable homes and lack jobs who are fighting against hunger. Households in rural areas are experiencing higher rates of food insecurity than metro areas. According to *The Conversation*, 48 million Americans face hunger and food insecurity across our nation. In several states in the South, the lack of education, poverty, programs, and the social infrastructure³ all combine and further deepens to problems of hunger.

The USDA’s *Economic Research Service*, has shown that households that are food-insecure, eat a less varied diet, take part in federal food assistant programs (Food Stamps), and struggle with expenses.⁴ The underlying problem of food insecurity is the cycle of constantly struggling with the issues that come with hunger such as food payments and bills. Hunger has been with us for centuries and heard of just about everywhere. We learned from our history that people suffered from hunger because of failed crops, natural disasters, lack of resources, no animals to hunt, etc. At that time, such occurrences were phenomenons that pushed back society and prohibited them from their meals. In today’s society, we have a much better grasp on how to deal with these events, yet the rates of hunger keeps rising.

The concept of food security is quite a simple concept. There will always be people who have enough to eat and then there’s people who don’t. The Department of Agriculture survey shows that a comparison between the percentage of households experiencing food insecurity in 1995 to nowadays have climbed up. Many people may be thinking that this is due to changes in the economy. The overall U.S. economy has grown roughly 60 % over the same period which

³ The Conversation. (2016). U.S is a Land of Plenty, so Why Do Americans Go Hungry?. Retrieved August 6, 2020, from <https://theconversation.com/u-s-is-a-land-of-plenty-so-why-do-millions-of-americans-still-go-hungry-55791>

⁴ Canning, P. (2020). Resource Requirement of Food Demand in the United States. Retrieved August 10, 2020, from <https://www.ers.usda.gov/publications/pub-details/?pubid=98400>

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indicates that economic gains alone are not improving the lives of the most vulnerable.⁵ In other words, hunger doesn't simply correlate with just the economy of different states. There are so many other factors that all add up to the rates of hunger in the U.S such as poverty and the public's lack of access to fundamental resources. The challenge of hunger is a deepening cycle of malnutrition, persistent poverty, and limited economic and education poverty.

Within this everlasting cycle, food insecurity and hunger in the U.S immoderately affect children and their families' lives. Nearly 1 in 7 households with children are unable to sufficiently buy food for their families and often struggle cannot buy enough food for their families. The food insecurity rate for households with children (13.9 percent) is two-fifths higher than the rate for households without children (9.9 percent).⁶ This evidently paints the picture that the children affected by such hunger rates come from low-income families that struggle to obtain adequate meals, shelter, and education. When children go hungry, they face a higher risk of health conditions, more frequently get hospitalized, lack proper education, are unable to receive proper nutrients, and brain activity is affected. Shelly Callahn highlights in her article that children who lack the proper food or nutrition are more likely to face obstacles that setback their path out of poverty.⁷ The federal food programs the country provides do help the people, but at what cost? In every 100 school lunch programs, there are only 87 breakfast sites and merely 36 summer food programs.

Yet, policymakers are quick to refute arguments regarding the excessive number of children who go hungry because their area doesn't provide the proper food banks and programs. Many programs that fail to instigate real change through their advertising lead to a higher rate of child hunger. It's clear that the policymakers are not receiving the message or properly taking action. American children go hungry in this prosperous nation on a regular basis and despite the high economy, food insecurity is consistently put aside and neglected. These problems are rooted from one origin, and it's the government. In the *Journal of Applied Research on Children*, food programs with a proven track record of addressing food insecurity "should be available and easily accessible" to children and their families. The programs include food stamps or SNAP,

⁵ Bureau of Economic Analysis. (2020). BEA Updates Regional Economic Tool. Retrieved August 7, 2020, from <https://www.bea.gov/>

⁶ Food Research & Action Center. (2018). Hunger & Poverty in America. Retrieved August 8, 2020, from <https://frac.org/hunger-poverty-america>

⁷ Callahan, S. (2020). *Facts About Child Hunger and Poverty*. Children Incorporated. Retrieved August 11, 2020, from <https://childrenincorporated.org/facts-about-child-hunger-and-poverty/>

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WIC, and free or reduced-price school breakfast and lunch.⁸ Millions of low-income children depend on food assistance programs and each year the numbers keep on rising.

Studies show that roughly a quarter of children in Texas live in poverty and the state ranks above the national average percentage of food insecure households. Texas ranks above the national average in the percentage of food insecure households, and roughly one quarter of Texas' children live in poverty. In over 2,000 schools in Texas, 80% of the student population are economically disadvantaged and lack the proper funds to have access to numerous food programs. This is why policy change is so essential and we must demand universal free school lunches and breakfast. By implementing these changes, the overall health, academics, student participation, and mental health will elevate. These strides were made to increase low-income communities' access to fresh, healthy foods.

Industry leaders, non-profit advocates, officials, and policymakers have combined their efforts to provide more access to fresh food in areas that are dense in food insecurity. However, the truth is that many of the Americans who are food insecure are still neglected by the government and this perpetuates the ideology that the government should not play such a heavy role when it comes to feeding the hungry. Those who specialize in food programs and agriculture should decide and simply receive the proper funds from the government. Even if families take advantage of the resources provided in federal food assistance programs, there will always be a set amount of people who are not receiving the proper nourishments. The balance is always being tipped off.

It is unfortunate for those affected by hunger in times of poverty. How many times in your life have you ever felt such hunger that makes your stomach cave in and cry out in pain. Maybe when craving was felt, you went to nourish yourself with a meal or a quick snack. This is not the case for everyone. Not everyone out there has the same opportunities as another person. Too many people go hungry in a nation that has the means to feed every mouth. We must ask ourselves, what can we as individuals do to help decrease the rates of hunger and poverty? Whether it affects you directly or not, this prevalent issue has been around for so long and too many have suffered because of it. While it's evident that hunger and poverty can't fully disappear at the blink of an eye, every step towards that goal will benefit everyone. Several small solutions that everyone can take part in are supporting non-profit organizations and sites that aid

⁸ Sanborn, Robert D. and Giardino, Angelo P. (2012) "Food Insecurity and Children: Hunger?... In America?... How is that possible?," *Journal of Applied Research on Children: Informing Policy for Children at Risk*: Vol. 3 : Iss. 1 , Article 2. Retrieved August 10, 2020, from <https://digitalcommons.library.tmc.edu/childrenatrisk/vol3/iss1/2>

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food assistance. The data collected through *Feeding America* continues to help guide program development that seeks to improve food security for individuals and their households.

In 2014, reports found that the *Feeding America* network of food banks provides service to 46.5 million people in need across the United States, including 12 million children and 7 million seniors.⁹ Through a network of 58,000 pantries, meal service programs, and other charitable food programs, the Feeding America network serves 5.4 million individuals each week. Actions like these truly benefit a large group of hungry people and decrease the rates of food insecurity. Many people do question the effectiveness of such an organization as to how they get their resources. Obtaining fresh, healthy food for the hungry is not a matter of the lack of resources, especially in a country that produces 430 billion pounds of food annually, and that is nearly enough to feed 400 million people! The population of the United States is not quite 329 million.¹⁰ We have heard it everywhere that there is enough food to feed our country and help eliminate the hungry and the poor. Nevertheless, we are throwing away more than 40 % of it. Every day we throw out meals that we don't feel like finishing and put them to waste. All that food that goes to waste and we don't think much of it. No. Maybe it does flash through our mind, the devastating looks of hungry families and people who don't know what it feels like to have several meals a day.

According to RTS, each year about 80 billion pounds of food is thrown out in the U.S. It's already a scary image in mind especially when that amount can be compared to 1,000 Empire State Buildings.¹¹ So what can we do now? Just reading this to yourself won't create change. Laws should be more heavily enforced in food wastes in restaurants, schools, public facilities, events, and work. Several things that every individual can keep in mind is to be mindful of the foods they eat, double check expiration dates, advocate for your favorite local restaurants to donate their leftover food to the hungry, reducing food waste in commercial businesses, and definitely implement rules where school foods will be donated to homeless shelters and the poor. We can take this initiative one state at a time and track the progress over a span of 5 years. I am confident that with time, effort, and heart we can work towards a decline in food waste and hunger.

It's not that we don't do anything to help solve hunger and malnourishment. In fact, we made great strides in reducing hunger as a nation before the late 1970s-1980s where numerous

⁹ Feeding America. (2020). Hunger in America Study. Retrieved August 11,2020, from <https://www.feedingamerica.org/research/hunger-in-america>

¹⁰ Stanley, A. (2014). A Better Way to End Hunger in America. Retrieved August 11,2020 from <https://www.wbur.org/cognoscenti/2014/09/17/hunger-in-america-food-distribution-ashley-stanley>

¹¹ RTS. (2020). Food Waste in America. Retrieved August 11,2020, from <https://www.rts.com/resources/guides/food-waste-america/>

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cuts were made from hunger relief programs to private charities. Not quite a surprise that because of this action, hunger in America has risen exponentially just like the charities that attempt to alleviate it. Organizations in the United States that fight against hunger grow to become huge, multi-million dollar agencies and they often are completely isolated from the communities they serve. Despite what we believe, stopping hunger doesn't require expensive scientific analysis, vaccines or billions of funds. What it requires is connecting existing resources to people that need it and providing a network of programs that can help aid the process. The question applies to hunger on the global scale, as well. It's never the issue that there isn't enough food; it's not enough people getting it and not enough people caring to help out. With the right people, resources, industries, and officials this is a relatively inexpensive solution that concurrently addresses the financial, environmental and health costs and consequences of wasting food.

Hope has not been lost yet. In fact, now more than ever people are working together to create programs and services that will substantially decrease the rates of hunger within minority groups, poor, and the homeless. We can no longer talk about hunger relief without also addressing the politics around food. We need to advocate for more jobs, a true living wage and better federal nutrition programs to truly end the epidemic. We need a long view that meets hunger exactly where it is right now. Our interns at *FINXERUNT* are working hard to help solve and provide more information about socioeconomic issues worldwide. With their help, we can build a project that will allow us to collaborate with researchers, finances, businessmen, and other organizations. By combining our sources we will start a program that will help us decrease hunger rate throughout America; one step at a time. Every step starts with you. It's about everyone taking their part from individuals to large corporations - initiative and small changes all combine to make a big difference.

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